

THE CONCEPT OF CHILDHOOD IN THE SCIENTIFIC AND ARTISTIC TRADITIONS OF THE XX CENTURY

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Abstract

In itself, the concept of childhood is complex and is interpreted by different fields of science in their own way. However, this does not mean that the phenomenon of childhood refers only to a certain stage of the formation of society. As you know, each society, individually, has its own ideas about childhood; accordingly, childhood is a cultural phenomenon. The question is what was the attitude of society towards the younger generation. The interaction of society with the childhood period has undergone changes from its complete disregard as a time extremely important in the formation of personality in traditional culture, to the recognition of the child as a full member of society in the process of active socialization in the era of industrialization. Therefore, the study of the concept of "childhood" is primarily associated with changes in society that follow in a certain period of time.

Keywords: Concept, childhood, cultural phenomenon, society, psychology, physiology, lexical–semantic field, active socialization, era of industrialization, ambivalent interpretations, positive connotations, non–age component, personal paradigm, primarily a creator, child's thinking, spiritual life, emotional sphere.

Introduction.

Currently, the term concept is a key concept in cognitive linguistics. Despite the fact that the concept of concept can be considered established for modern cognitive science, the content of this concept varies significantly in the concepts of individual scientists and different scientific schools.

The fact is that a concept is a category of thought, unobservable, and this gives a lot of scope for its interpretation. The concept category appears today in the research of philosophers, logicians, psychologists, and cultural scientists, and it bears the traces of all these extra-linguistic interpretations.

For the first time in science, the term concept was used by S.A. Askold-Alekseev. The scientist defined the concept as a mental formation that replaces an indefinite set of objects, actions, and mental functions of the same kind in the process of thought. He believed that the most important function of concepts is the function of substitution, since, being a mental formation, the concept replaces many objects of the same kind in the process of thought.

A concept can replace both real objects and some aspects of an object or real actions. E.S. Kubryakova offers the following definition of the concept: "Concept) is a unit of mental or mental resources of our consciousness; an operational meaningful unit of memory, mental lexicon, conceptual system and language of the brain (*lingua mentalis*), the whole picture of the world reflected in the human psyche [Kubryakova, 2001: 90].

In the processes of thinking, a person operates with concepts that reflect the content of the results of human activity and knowledge of the world in the form of certain "quanta" of knowledge." This is information about what an individual assumes, thinks, knows and imagines about the objects of the world.

Cognitive science cannot yet answer the question of how concepts arise, except by pointing to the process of formation of meanings in the most general form. It is believed that language provides the best access to the description and definition of the nature of concepts. At the same time, some scientists believe that as the sim-

plest concepts should be considered concepts represented by a single word, and as more complex ones – those that are presented in phrases and sentences.

According to Polish linguist A. Wierzbicka, a concept is an object of an ideal world that has a name and reflects certain culturally conditioned human ideas about the real world (Wierzbicka, 2003: 263).

It is recognized that the concept is the main unit of the conceptual sphere. According to modern ideas about the non-verbal nature of human thinking, it is believed that the conceptsphere as a community of concepts exists autonomously, regardless of the linguistic means of its expression, objectification.

A concept can act as a complex thinking unit that turns in different directions in the process of mental activity, actualizing its different signs and layers in the process of mental activity; the corresponding signs or layers of the concept may well have signs and layers; the corresponding signs or layers of the concept may well not have a linguistic designation in the native language of a person.

Representatives of the Voronezh Scientific School – Z.D. Popova, I.A. Sternin and others consider the concept as a global thought a unit representing a "quantum of structured knowledge"

In their opinion, the concept is represented in the language by lexemes, phrases, phrases, sentences, texts and sets of texts. Having considered the linguistic expressions of the concept, we can get an idea of its content in the minds of native speakers.

Yu. S. Stepanov considers the "concept" from a cultural point of view: "A concept is like a clot of culture in a person's mind; that in which culture enters the mental world of a person. And, on the other hand, a concept is something by which a person is an ordinary, ordinary person, not a "creator cultural values" — enters culture itself, and in some cases influences it" (Stepanov, 2003: 231).

Analyzing these concepts, it can be concluded that the researchers have not come to a common understanding of the term "concept". There are three main directions or approaches to understanding a concept in science: linguistic, cognitive, and cultural.

In addition, the concept has a very complex multi-dimensional structure. It can distinguish both the concrete and the abstract, both rational and emotional, both universal and ethnic, both national and individual-personal. This explains the lack of a single definition.

The theme of childhood in world literature is one of the most relevant, socially and psychologically significant topics. It is touched upon in many works: this may be the main motive in the narrative, or it may be only a fragment, a small part of the entire work. The image of childhood belongs to the number of traditional objects of research by scientists from various fields of science, in addition to philology: psychology, sociology, pedagogy, philosophy, etc.

Research methods. Childhood is a complex cultural phenomenon. There are many formulations characterizing this concept. In the explanatory dictionary of the Russian language by S. I. Ojegov, childhood is defined as "early, pre-adolescence age; the period of life at that age." In psychology and physiology, childhood is also interpreted as one of the stages of ontogenesis, determined by specific age limits.

The concept of "childhood" includes the concept of time, so it can be attributed to "age-related" concepts. Not the whole life of a person is considered, but only a certain period (from birth to adulthood). In addition, this concept can be attributed to national (universal), since regardless of nationality, there is a period of childhood in every person's life. Based on the data of Associative Dictionary, childhood can be considered as a contradictory period. On the one hand, childhood is understood as a carefree, happy, cheerful, joyful, but irrevocable time of human life, and on the other hand – as a difficult and difficult period. An important characteristic of childhood is also the place in which it takes place. Despite the fact that the concept of "childhood", like any other concept, has ambivalent interpretations, it is much more often represented by positive connotations.

The child is the subject of the concept of "childhood". Its meaning is not identical to the concept of "child", since the defined lexical-semantic field is much wider and is located in the space of the conceptual sphere next to "time", but at the same time it certainly absorbs some signs of this related concept. Of great importance are the features that characterize the child's worldview, the child's thinking, his spiritual life and the emotional sphere:

- 1) children's mythologism;
- 2) play as the main form of children's activity;
- 3) an extraordinarily wide and rich world of children's fantasy;
- 4) the integrity of the child's soul, its naivety and spontaneity, the absence of any division in the child, artificiality, spiritual and mental health;
- 5) freedom from stereotypes, norms and conventions, freedom of expression of feelings, spiritual freedom;
- 6) Creative energy.

In the structure of the concept under study, the opposition of childhood as the initial period of a person's life to adulthood (maturity) is clearly expressed as the highest level of physical and intellectual development his development. With the development of ideas about

childhood as a kind of state of mind, this opposition in relation to spiritual life is not so categorical.

According to C. Jung, every personality has the archetypal properties of a child. The conventional metaphorical concept of childhood is actualized in the traditional cultural discourse.

In this case, the phenomenon of childhood is not limited to physiological connotations, but can be interpreted as "an integral and non-age component of the personal paradigm of a person, primarily a creator.

Philosophical and psychological theories, the subject of which is the personality of a child, indicate the presence of a creative component in the structure of the concept of "childhood". Based on F. Nietzsche's theory, which develops the idea of superman, the child is thought of not just as an example of free creativity and an extraordinary worldview, but as the highest stage of creative self-improvement.

The child, according to F. Nietzsche, is "innocence and oblivion, a new beginning, a game, a rolling wheel, an initial movement, the holy word of affirmation." This is the last stage of the "transformation of the spirit", the purity and "innocence" of which mean freedom from any norms and values and imply endless variability of self-actualization.

In E. Bern's theory, the concept of "child" is considered to determine the nature of a person's worldview as a whole. According to E. Bern's personality model, the child is one of the most valuable components of personality, since it is a source of intuition, creativity, spontaneous impulses and joy.

3. Freud compared children playing with artists, as they create their own world, similar to the "artistic" one, and take it absolutely sincerely and seriously, putting into their game all the passion and emotions that children are capable of. Thus, in philosophical and psychological discourses, the preservation by an adult of the properties inherent in childhood ("childishness") is often interpreted as "the preservation of creative possibilities and immediacy of world perception, which is a sign of a creative personality"

In the modern artistic process, many professionals create or use the most diverse childhood images as the main creative material. For different types of art, it is of interest to highlight common and specific expressive means used by the authors to create an image of childhood.

In analyzing the image of childhood, O. O. Gracheva in the article "Images of childhood in art: aspects of humanitarian analysis" uses psychological and pedagogical concepts, the consideration of which allows us to identify the archetypes of childhood. These are images of a child – an object of care and attention an adult and a child – a miniature model of an adult. These archetypes consider childhood as a natural and inevitable period, but burdensome for adults. Such characteristics are characteristic of works about children created within the framework of primitive art, the era of ancient civilizations, Antiquity, and the Middle Ages. In these cultures, children's images are presented conditionally, they do not so much depict as denote the most important characteristics of childhood. The only positive thing about a child is the prospect of growth and improvement.

Therefore, childhood symbolizes the beginning, renewal and rebirth, it is, above all, hope for the future. In the perception of adults, children symbolize hope, purity, optimism, embodying the most positive concepts. Thus, the third archetype of childhood can be distinguished - the symbolic use of this image in art.

The typology of images is expanding in the period of modern and modern times. In different types of art, one can find works created within the framework of new types, including newly emerging (man-made).

O. O. Gracheva considers the following types to be new types of children's images: the recipient child. This image appears when you get acquainted with works of various types of art addressed to children. From about the end of the XVIII century, professional works created specifically for children's audiences began to appear, the main task of which is to deliver aesthetic pleasure for the child, to lay the foundations for the aesthetic development of the personality. It was only in the second half of the 19th century that works appeared that created a true image of the child as an autonomous developing personality.

Such a holistic, self-valuable aesthetic and psychological characteristics of the image of childhood has an impact on the emergence of a fundamentally new phenomenon in art. This is a child subject whose activity is embodied by an adult in works of art addressed to an audience of all ages (children, adults, and both). The youngest in terms of time of occurrence is the image of a child creator, independently creating a work of art. Society is beginning to realize that children's creativity is valuable in itself. A real breakthrough is taking place in the art of the 20th century: adults are beginning to appreciate children's creativity, first of all, its childishness.

It is not so much the "adult" creative skills that are of particular value, as the emotional colors characteristic of childhood and specific means of expression.

Conclusion. The analysis of children's images in art using psychological and pedagogical concepts allows us to identify archetypal (child – object, child – model and child – symbol) and new variants of types of children's images (child – recipient, child – interpreter, child – self – valuable personality and child – creator).

The specified meanings related to the central zone of meaning the concept "childhood" varies in different ways in the works of art by various authors, being enriched by individual ideas about this multifaceted phenomenon of "childhood".

The study of the phenomenon of childhood in the cultural aspect of the study allowed us to reveal the main semantic components of the concept of "childhood" and to study the peculiarities of the formation of the image of childhood in the history of fine art. The systematization of modern theoretical concepts in this field has made it possible to form the main theses that determine the solution of the tasks of the ongoing research.

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